

ELECTRONIC BANKING UTILIZATION AND CLIENTS' SATISFACTION IN A UNIVERSAL BANK OF LAGUNA

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ABSTRACT

The banking industry embraced technological innovation created an extended banking services high in efficiency, convenience, and security which increased and boost clients' satisfaction. However, this digital transformation became a great challenge to financial institutions because some clients, particularly in a Universal Bank in Laguna, were not ready to fully utilized the advantages of electronic banking services. This study investigated the level of electronic banking utilization which affected the clients' satisfaction level in a Universal Bank. The study employed a descriptive correlational design and utilized the stratified random sampling technique that determined the number of respondents which consisted of three hundred ten (310) Universal Bank clients across thirty-one (31) Universal Bank branches located in Laguna. The findings revealed that electronic banking utilization was widely utilized in terms of website efficiency (3.56), user-friendliness (3.51) customer service (3.33), and security (3.00). In terms of clients' satisfaction, efficiency (3.42), system availability (3.37), fulfilment (3.44), and Privacy (2.96) were constantly satisfied. Furthermore, a statistically significant relationship was identified between the electronic banking utilization and clients' satisfaction, as indicated by probability values below 0.05 threshold, which was led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. In addition, based on the result, the proposed action plan intensified the utilization of electronic banking and ensured that client-centric approach extended the clients' digital banking experience. The plan enhanced electronic banking data security, data privacy, and customer service that provided clients a more reliable digital banking experience with optimum protections and more efficient banking solutions. This indicated that electronic banking utilization has a significant effect on client satisfaction in terms of fulfilment, which constitutes with probability values.

Keywords: *Electronic Banking Utilization, Clients' Satisfaction, Efficiency, Security, and Privacy*

INTRODUCTION

The banking industry consistently embraces technological innovation to create extended banking services that are high in efficiency, convenience, and security to increase and boost clients' satisfaction. The competition in the financial sector has rapidly increased, consistently innovating to elevate the quality of electronic banking services. As competition intensifies, financial institutions keep on pushing their limit to increase the competence of their service quality. Furthermore, over time, clients' expectations increased and transformed rapidly reason for the bank to provide constant services for their clients to access their accounts anytime, anywhere.

However, this digital transformation has become a great challenge to financial institutions to protect their clients' finances against market threats and challenges in sustaining and retaining their clients' trust and confidence in doing business with them. Although various issues arise along the way, banks never stopped recalibrating their system to increase barriers and to mitigate the negative effects that their client may possibly encounter. Optimizing the service quality of electronic banking services, focusing on the client experience, will effectively address challenges towards the leveraging of the advances of technology, which led to significant banking productivity.

Furthermore, at the altitude of intensified and rapid competition within the banking sectors, prioritize the delivery of exceptional electronic banking services to maintain their market competency. Moreover, the financial industry pushes financial institutions to maximize their presence of innovation and adaptation in order to assess the challenges that cause adverse effects on their performance and provide assurance of high-quality services for their clients. According to the study conducted by Salmanov (2024), electronic banking greatly influenced client satisfaction around the world. It was essential for financial institutions not to have reduced their operational expenses in order to continuously improve the platform. This allowed them to maximize their access to a broader market, generate new sources of revenue, and significantly impact the financial performance of banks.

Meanwhile, Indriasari et al. (2022) mentioned that the utilization of electronic banking can be challenging to the banking industry since several challenges in the process may include the efficiency of the platform and the adverse risk of the clients towards the environmental risk, data, and security breach while performing the application.

According to the article by Pearlpay (2021, as quoted in Balmes 2023), mentioned that in the Philippines, only 42.1% of internet users maximized the usage of electronic banking and financial service applications. However, in the Philippines, with a record of 110.3 million population, only 46.44 million Filipinos had access to financial services,

while 63.86 million have yet to. This implied that one of the barriers to banking sectors in the Philippines is the lack of client access to the platform.

In relation to the proceeding article of (Calamba City Promotes Digital Payments, Rolls Out Paleng-QR Ph Plus - FintechNewsPh, 2024) deduced that through the utilization of electronic banking transactions, clients could monitor their financial activities at any time of the, anywhere to manage their finances effectively.

Moreover, electronic banking has challenges not only in the Philippines but all over the world since cyberattacks are vulnerable in the banking industry, this technical problem disrupts banking services, causing clients hesitations to maximize the usage of the digital platform since the client's concerns remain prevalent regarding electronic banking security and data privacy, providing effective resolution to this issue will ensure seamless clients' online banking services on Universal Bank in Laguna. Moreover, understanding the essentials of electronic banking to examine its transformative impact on the banking sector, even in society and the economy, since this action may provide the financial institutions insights on how to leverage technology to elevate financial inclusivity by improving bank operation efficiency to mitigate the associated financial risk to enhance the client satisfaction.

Furthermore, the implementation of electronic banking in a Universal Bank in Laguna was successful and provided effective banking services. However, some clients in the Universal Bank in Laguna had not enrolled and were not ready to utilize electronic banking. This study comprehensively examined the extent to which electronic banking was utilized within a Universal Bank in Laguna. It aimed to assess the satisfaction levels of enrolled clients and determine the effectiveness of electronic banking services in meeting their financial needs. Additionally, it provided valuable insights into the factors influencing the hesitance of non-enrolled clients, exploring the barriers that prevent them from fully embracing digital banking solutions. The study sought to offer recommendations that could enhance user adoption, improve service delivery, and ultimately strengthen the efficiency of electronic banking within the institution.

Research Questions

The study identified the significance of electronic banking utilization and clients' satisfaction with Universal Bank in Laguna. It sought to answer specifically the following questions:

1. What is the level of electronic banking utilization in a Universal Bank in Laguna as assessed by clients in terms of:
 - 1.1. Website efficiency,
 - 1.2. User-Friendliness,
 - 1.3. Customer Service, and
 - 1.4. Security?
2. What is the clients' satisfaction level in a Universal Bank in Laguna in terms of:

- 2.1. Efficiency,
- 2.2. System Availability,
- 2.3. Fulfillment, and
- 2.4. Privacy?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of electronic banking utilization and the clients' satisfaction level in a Universal Bank in Laguna?
4. Does the level of electronic banking utilization significantly impact clients' satisfaction level in a Universal Bank in Laguna?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in thirty-one Universal Bank branches across three clusters in Laguna. The first cluster, Laguna A, consisted of branches located in San Pedro, Biñan, and Sta. Rosa North. The second cluster, Laguna B, included branches in Calamba, Los Baños, Sta. Cruz, and Pagsanjan. Lastly, the Laguna C cluster comprised branches in Sta. Rosa South, Cabuyao, and Canlubang.

Stratified random sampling was employed to select participants from the diverse pool of clients enrolled in electronic banking at Universal Bank. The total population size consisted of 300,000 electronic banking clients across the thirty-one branches in Laguna. Using G*Power, the sample size was determined to be 110 respondents from Cluster A, 100 from Cluster B, and 100 from Cluster C, totaling 310 respondents.

Before data collection commenced, informed consent was obtained from participants. Full disclosure regarding the study's objectives was provided to ensure ethical compliance. The primary research instrument was a researcher-made questionnaire, specifically designed to assess electronic banking utilization and client satisfaction at Universal Bank in Laguna.

The first section of the questionnaire focused on the extent of electronic banking utilization, covering dimensions such as website efficiency, user-friendliness, customer service, and security. The second section assessed client satisfaction, examining aspects such as efficiency, system availability, fulfillment, and privacy. Responses were gathered using a 4-point Likert scale, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of utilization and satisfaction levels. Numerical scores were assigned to each response to quantify attitudes and preferences.

The Level of Electronic Banking Utilization questionnaire underwent a thorough validation process. The Content Validity Index (CVI) values for its components were as follows: Website Efficiency (1.00), User-Friendliness (1.00), Customer Service (1.00), and Security (1.00), indicating excellent content validity. The reliability of the questionnaire was confirmed with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.946, demonstrating high internal consistency.

Similarly, the Client Satisfaction Level questionnaire underwent a thorough validation process. The CVI values for its components were: Efficiency (1.00), System Availability (1.00), Fulfillment (1.00), and Privacy (1.00), again indicating excellent content validity. Its reliability was confirmed with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.944, further demonstrating high internal consistency.

Thus, the instruments used in the study were both valid and reliable, ensuring their appropriateness for assessing the research objectives.

For data analysis, a range of statistical techniques was employed based on the study variables. The mean and 4-point Likert scale were used to determine average scores for the level of electronic banking utilization and client satisfaction. To identify any significant relationship between these two variables, Pearson's product-moment correlation was used. This technique enabled the identification of potential correlations between electronic banking utilization metrics and client satisfaction indicators such as efficiency, system availability, fulfillment, and privacy.

Furthermore, multiple linear regression analysis was applied to assess the impact of electronic banking utilization on client satisfaction. This statistical method allowed for the simultaneous examination of how utilization metrics influenced various satisfaction components, yielding valuable insights into electronic banking practices at Universal Bank in Laguna.

The study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design to assess the level of electronic banking utilization (in terms of website efficiency, user-friendliness, customer service, and security) and determine its relationship with client satisfaction (in terms of efficiency, system availability, fulfillment, and privacy).

Participants were selected from thirty-one Universal Bank branches in Laguna, including locations in San Pedro, Biñan, Sta. Rosa North, Sta. Rosa South, Canlubang, Cabuyao, Calamba, Los Baños, Sta. Cruz, and Pagsanjan. As of December 2024, approximately 300,000 individuals were enrolled in Universal Bank's electronic banking services.

However, the study acknowledged certain limitations. It focused solely on electronic banking utilization and did not cover other types of banking services. Additionally, the geographical scope was restricted to Universal Bank branches within the province of Laguna.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 Level of Electronic Banking Utilization in Universal Bank in Laguna as assessed by Clients in terms of Website Efficiency

Indicators	\bar{X} Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The electronic banking website's layout is intuitive and easy to navigate.	3.67	Fully Utilized	1
2. The electronic banking website provides a seamless experience across different devices.	3.54	Fully Utilized	3
3. The electronic banking website's login process is straightforward and user-friendly.	3.56	Fully Utilized	2
4. The electronic banking website loads quickly and efficiently.	3.51	Fully Utilized	4
5. The electronic banking website's error handling is efficient, providing clear messages and guidance when issues arise.	3.50	Fully Utilized	5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.56	Fully Utilized	

Legend:

3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Utilized	1.75-2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Utilized
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Utilized	1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Utilized

Table 1.2 Level of Electronic Banking Utilization in Universal Bank in Laguna as assessed by Clients in terms of User-Friendliness

Indicators	\bar{X} Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The electronic banking system provides clear instructions and guidance for performing various transactions.	3.44	Fully Utilized	1
2. The language used in the electronic banking system is simple and jargon-free, making it accessible to all users.	3.42	Fully Utilized	3
3. The process of setting up and managing accounts within the electronic banking system is straightforward.	3.43	Fully Utilized	2

4. Error messages within the electronic banking system are helpful and provide guidance on how to resolve issues.	3.34	Fully Utilized	5
5. Help and support resources are readily available within the electronic banking system for users who need assistance.	3.39	Fully Utilized	4
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.41	Fully Utilized	

Legend:

3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Utilized 1.75-2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Utilized
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Utilized 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Utilized

Table 1.3 Level of Electronic Banking Utilization in Universal Bank in Laguna is assessed by Clients in terms of Customer Service

Indicators	\bar{X} Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Electronic banking customer service representatives are readily available to assist customers when needed.	3.45	Fully Utilized	1
2. The response time for inquiries made through electronic banking customer service channels is satisfactory.	3.29	Fully Utilized	4
3. Electronic banking customer service agents are knowledgeable and able to address customer queries effectively.	3.31	Fully Utilized	3
4. The electronic banking customer service team handles complaints and issues in a timely and satisfactory manner.	3.26	Fully Utilized	5
5. Electronic banking customer service agents demonstrate professionalism and courtesy in their interactions with customers.	3.35	Fully Utilized	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.33	Fully Utilized	

Legend:

3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Utilized 1.75-2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Utilized
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Utilized 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Utilized

Table 1.4 Level of Electronic Banking Utilization in Universal Bank in Laguna as assessed by Clients in terms of Security

Indicators	\bar{X} Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The security measures implemented by electronic banking platforms effectively protect customer accounts from unauthorized access.	3.07	Utilized	1
2. Electronic banking platforms provide clear information about security measures and recommendations to users.	2.94	Utilized	5
3. Users have confidence in the security of electronic banking platforms to safeguard their financial information.	3.03	Utilized	2
4. Electronic banking platforms promptly notify users of any suspicious activities or security breaches affecting their accounts.	2.97	Utilized	3.5
5. Electronic banking systems effectively detect and prevent fraudulent activities, such as phishing or identity theft.	2.97	Utilized	3.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.00	Utilized	

Legend:

3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Utilized 1.75-2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Utilized
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Utilized 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Utilized

Table 2.1 Level of Clients' Satisfaction in Electronic Banking at Universal Bank in Laguna in terms of Efficiency

Indicators	\bar{X} Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Electronic banking systems are more efficient than traditional banking	3.49	Highly Satisfied	1
2. Electronic banking provides sufficient customer support options for addressing issues or concerns.	3.39	Highly Satisfied	4.5
3. Electronic banking facilitates easier access to financial services for individuals in remote or underserved areas.	3.41	Highly Satisfied	3

4. Electronic banking reduces the risk of human error in financial transactions.	3.39	Highly Satisfied	4.5
5. Electronic banking improves the overall efficiency and convenience of banking processes.	3.42	Highly Satisfied	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.42	Highly Satisfied	

Legend:
 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Utilized 1.75-2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Utilized
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Utilized 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Utilized

Table 2.2 Level of Clients' Satisfaction in Electronic Banking at Universal Bank in Laguna in terms of System Availability

Indicators	\bar{X} Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Electronic banking systems provide reliable and consistent availability to meet customer needs.	3.39	Highly Satisfied	2.5
2. Electronic banking systems are consistently available during peak usage hours.	3.34	Highly Satisfied	4
3. Electronic banking services experience minimal downtime due to maintenance or system updates.	3.32	Highly Satisfied	5
4. Customers can access electronic banking systems across various devices without encountering significant technical issues.	3.39	Highly Satisfied	2.5
5. Customers rarely encounter system errors or glitches when using electronic banking services.	3.40	Highly Satisfied	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.37	Highly Satisfied	

Legend:
 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Utilized 1.75-2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Utilized
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Utilized 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Utilized

Table 2.3 Level of Clients' Satisfaction in Electronic Banking at Universal Bank in Laguna in terms of Fulfillment

Indicators	\bar{X} Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Electronic banking services fulfill the needs of most customers.	3.46	Highly Satisfied	1
2. The availability of electronic banking services meets the demands of customers in terms of uptime and reliability.	3.40	Highly Satisfied	5
3. The customization options available in electronic banking platforms adequately meet individual customer needs.	3.43	Highly Satisfied	4
4. Electronic banking platforms provide sufficient flexibility in terms of fund transfers and payment options.	3.45	Highly Satisfied	2.5
5. Electronic banking fulfills the majority of customer expectations and requirements in modern banking.	3.45	Highly Satisfied	2.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.44	Highly Satisfied	

Legend:

3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Utilized	1.75-2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Utilized
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Utilized	1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Utilized

Table 2.4 Level of Clients' Satisfaction in Electronic Banking at Universal Bank in Laguna in terms of Privacy

Indicators	\bar{X} Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Electronic banking platforms adequately protect the privacy of customer data.	3.11	Satisfied	1
2. Electronic banking platforms provide transparent policies regarding the collection and usage of customer data.	2.98	Satisfied	2
3. Customers trust electronic banking systems to keep their financial information confidential.	2.93	Satisfied	3

4. Electronic banking platforms promptly notify customers in case of any privacy-related incidents or breaches.	2.87	Satisfied	5
5. Electronic banking systems prioritize the privacy and security of customer data.	2.90	Satisfied	4

GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.96	Satisfied
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Legend:

3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Fully Utilized	1.75-2.49 Disagree (D)/ Partially Utilized
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Utilized	1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Utilized

Table 3 Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Electronic Banking Utilization and the Client Satisfaction Level in a Universal Bank in Laguna

Electronic banking utilization	Client satisfaction	R value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Website efficiency	Efficiency	.517**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	System Availability	.510**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Fulfillment	.547**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Privacy	.353**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
User-Friendliness	Efficiency	.581**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	System Availability	.566**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Fulfillment	.564**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Privacy	.383**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Customer Service	Efficiency	.562**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	System Availability	.606**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Fulfillment	.482**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Privacy	.461**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Security	Efficiency	.580**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	System Availability	.568**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Fulfillment	.473**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Privacy	.777**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Correlational at the level 0.01 (tailed)

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

Table 4.1 Regression Analysis on the Impact of Electronic Banking Utilization Level on the Client Satisfaction Level in a Universal Bank in Laguna in terms of Efficiency

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	.913	.171		5.339	.000		
Website efficiency	.155	.062	.139	2.488	.013	Reject Ho	Significant
User-Friendliness	.240	.060	.234	3.986	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Customer Service	.157	.046	.186	3.393	.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Security	.205	.033	.312	6.265	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Dependent Variable: Efficiency

R – Square = .494 F-value = 71.191
 Adjusted R Square = .487 Significance = .000

Table 4.2 Regression Analysis on the Impact of Electronic Banking Utilization Level on the Client Satisfaction Level in a Universal Bank in Laguna in terms of System Availability

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	.706	.182		3.883	.000		
Website efficiency	.148	.066	.124	2.245	.025	Reject Ho	Significant
User-	.209	.064	.191	3.259	.00	Reject	Significa

Friendliness					1	Ho	nt
Customer Service	.253	.049	.282	5.164	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Security	.193	.035	.276	5.562	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Variable: System Availability

R – Square = .499

Adjusted R Square = .492

F-value = 75.719

Significance = .000

Table 4.3 Regression Analysis on the Impact of Electronic Banking Utilization Level on the Client Satisfaction Level in a Universal Bank in Laguna in terms of Fulfillment

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	1.069	.172		6.230	.000		
Website efficiency	.264	.062	.252	4.228	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
User-Friendliness	.236	.060	.247	3.913	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Customer Service	.078	.046	.099	1.683	.093	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Security	.123	.033	.200	3.744	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Dependent Variable: Fulfillment

R – Square = .419

Adjusted R Square = .412

F-value = 54.901

Significance = .000

Table 4.4 Regression Analysis on the Impact of Electronic Banking Utilization Level on the Client Satisfaction Level in a Universal Bank in Laguna in terms of Privacy

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T			
(Constant)	.548	.216		2.533	.012		
Website efficiency	.065	.079	.041	.829	.408	Accept Ho	Not Significant
User-Friendliness	-.046	.076	-.031	-.604	.546	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Customer Service	.071	.058	.059	1.212	.226	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Security	.701	.041	.744	16.953	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Dependent Variable: Privacy

R – Square = .608 F-value = 117.838

Adjusted R Square = .603 Significance = .000

Proposed Action Plan

KEY AREAS	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	FREQUENCY	PERSONS INVOLVED	SECCES INDICATORS
Data Security	To enhance user verification methods to prevent unauthorized access.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduce multi-factor authentication for all transactions. - Implement biometric login (fingerprint and face recognition). - Strengthen password activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Every Transaction -Every system upgrade (Quarterly) - Every system upgrade (Quarterly) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IT Security Team. - Product Development Team. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 90% of digital banking users to enroll in multi-factor authentication security update. - Reduced unauthorized access incidents to 60%

		(e.g., minimum length, complexity, and expiration).			- 80% Increase in customer satisfaction with security features.
Data Privacy	Empower users to take control of their privacy through education and awareness programs.	- Conduct webinars about the importance of privacy, how their data is protected, and how they can control their information.	-Quarterly	- Risk management department head, - Bank personnel - Universal Bank clients located in Laguna.	Increase client awareness to 90% to combat and mitigate identity fraud.
Customer Service	To increase satisfaction and reduce customer complaints	- Implement surveys and feedback forms after transactions or at regular intervals. - identify pain points and areas for improvement. - Adapt platform features based on customer needs and preferences.	Feedback collection: Ongoing. Feedback analysis: Monthly. Platform adjustments: Quarterly or as needed.	Customer Support Team. Analytics Team.	80% compliance of clients' feedback 20% reduction customer complaints. 90% positive feedback and suggestions incorporated into platform updates.

DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the level of electronic banking utilization in a Universal Bank in Laguna as assessed by clients in terms of:

Table 1.1

Website Efficiency was Fully Utilized (3.56). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Utilized. Indicator number 1 “The electronic banking website’s layout is intuitive and easy to navigate” had the highest mean of 3.69 (Fully Utilized). Meanwhile, the indicator number 5 “The electronic banking website’s error handling is efficient, providing clear messages and guidance when issues arise” had the lowest mean of 3.27 (Fully Utilized).

This suggests that Universal Bank's electronic banking platform is highly regarded by clients for its website efficiency. Furthermore, clients demonstrate proficiency in navigating an intuitive website layout that ensures seamless transactions. However, they have also identified shortcomings in the website's error-handling guidelines. This highlights the need to enhance the FAQ section, allowing users to swiftly find solutions and significantly improve their digital banking experience.

In support to that, Shafee et al. (2022) mentioned that the alignment of the electronic banking application website with clients' preferences was essential to meeting their expectations and fully encouraging users to maximize the efficiency and effectiveness of the electronic banking platform. This implication was supported by the results of the study, which showed that Universal Bank clients enhanced their digital banking experience by increasing ease of use for more straightforward navigation.

Similarly, Getugi et al. (2023) stated that website efficiency was the primary aspect that significantly influenced users' experience and their intention to utilize digital banking services. They also mentioned that banks should have considered allocating funds for the continuous improvement of website efficiency to meet clients' preferred banking services in a timely manner. This indicated that although the Universal Bank electronic banking website was efficient, continuous investment in innovation was needed to effectively meet the rapidly changing client preferences and achieve greater market competency

Table 1.2

User-Friendliness was Fully Utilized (3.41). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Utilized. Indicator number 1 “The electronic banking system provides clear instructions and guidance for performing various transactions” had the highest mean of 3.44 (Fully Utilized). Meanwhile, the indicator number 4 “Error messages within the electronic banking system are helpful and provide guidance on how to resolve issues” had the lowest mean of 3.34 (Fully Utilized).

This implies that clients of Universal Bank hold high regard for the bank's ongoing efforts to provide digital banking users with precise and intuitive guidance, enabling them to efficiently navigate various transactions without inconvenience when exploring electronic banking services. This suggests that Universal Bank should enhance its electronic banking system by implementing an automatically generated listing system that promptly displays unavailable services in digital banking, including duration, frequency, and alternative options. By taking this action, Universal Bank strengthens its communication with clients, ensuring greater clarity and effectiveness for increased satisfaction.

The finding of the study was supported by Anyadighibe et al. (2023), who emphasized that interruptions and technical issues encountered by users while utilizing digital banking services caused frustration and dissatisfaction. This suggested that providing seamless and efficient guidelines to effectively resolve unpredictable issues would ensure the continuation of high-quality digital banking services that met clients' needs.

Apart from that, Kim et al. (2024) mentioned that leveraging system data to identify client behavioral patterns could help banks pinpoint areas for improvement in providing a seamless experience while utilizing digital banking services. Enhancing a user-friendly digital banking platform resulted in higher productivity for the bank, as users found it easier to navigate digital banking services with convenience and confidence. This suggested that Universal Bank should have elevated its transformable digital banking platform design with the clients in mind to effectively recalibrate and provide a smoother and more straightforward digital banking experience.

Table 1.3

Customer Service was Fully Utilized (3.33). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Fully Utilized. Indicator number 1 “Electronic banking customer service representatives are readily available to assist customers when needed” had the highest mean of 3.45 (Fully Utilized). Meanwhile, indicator number 4 “The electronic banking customer service team handles complaints and issues in a timely and satisfactory manner” had the lowest mean of 3.26 (Fully Utilized).

This implies that Universal Bank clients have a positive experience due to the professionalism of its customer service team, who are knowledgeable and ready to provide timely assistance in effectively resolving client concerns. This suggests that Universal Bank's commitment to enhancing after-service assistance brings significant improvements in how clients anticipate and utilize electronic banking services.

To reinforce these findings, Gautam & Sah (2023) emphasized that by focusing on customer service, banks strengthened and built long-term relationships with their clients. Providing immediate support and ensuring timely assistance encouraged users to continuously utilize the digital banking services provided. For this reason, Universal Bank had invested more in seminars to increase the competency of its customer service personnel, enabling them to handle clients' complaints more efficiently.

In line with this, Gracious Kaazara & Ariyo. (2023). illustrated that an absolute client experience in a digital banking platform could not have been achieved solely by having competitive digital banking charges. More importantly, it was the presence of high-quality customer service that had been readily available to address issues quickly and effectively, providing solutions to customer complaints for excellent extended banking services. By doing this, the lowest indicator in terms of customer service in electronic banking had been resolved, which led to higher satisfaction.

Table 1.4

Security was Utilized (3.00). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Utilized. Indicator number 1 “The security measures implemented by electronic banking platforms effectively protect customer accounts from unauthorized access” had the highest mean of 3.07 (Utilized). Meanwhile, indicator number 2 “Electronic banking platforms provide clear information about security measures and recommendations to users” had the lowest mean of 2.94 (Utilized).

This implies that the security measures implemented by electronic banking platforms effectively protect customer accounts from unauthorized access and are highly praised by clients, as they recognize Universal Bank's dedication and effort in combating cyber threats to ensure a safer digital environment. Meanwhile, electronic banking platforms provide clear information about security measures and recommendations, yet this aspect receives the lowest rating. This suggests that Universal Bank should introduce digital chatbots programmed to answer simple issues and concerns promptly and accurately, ensuring 24/7 availability. This initiative will enhance client engagement and boost their confidence in digital banking services.

According to (India Launches First Digital Threat Report 2024 to Support Cybersecurity in the Banking, Financial Services and Insurance (BFSI) Sector, n.d.), financial institutions had invested in educating their clients about the importance of electronic banking security measures to establish themselves as the first line of defense against fraud. This campaign provided clients with full awareness of how to protect their accounts from potential threats and uncertainties. Likewise, banks had intensified their efforts to enhance security protection, creating a safe financial environment for their clients. Furthermore, security had been the main concern for clients conducting business through digital banking. For that reason, Universal Bank continued innovating its digital platform by improving its security features to further safeguard clients from the possibility of financial loss.

Similarly, Sharma (2023) mentioned that financial institutions had fully integrated digital advancements to effectively navigate their systems and redesign their security business models to enhance system reassessment. This enabled the detection and mitigation of risks, increasing the implementation of security measures to provide excellent electronic banking service quality for users.

Research Question 2: What is the client's satisfaction level in a Universal Bank in Laguna in terms of:

Table 2.1

Efficiency was Highly Satisfied (3.42). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Highly Satisfied. Indicator number 1 "Electronic banking systems are more efficient than traditional banking" had the highest mean of 3.49 (Highly Satisfied). Meanwhile, indicator 2 "Electronic banking provides sufficient customer support options for addressing issues or concerns" and indicator 4 "Electronic banking reduces the risk of human error in financial transactions" had the lowest mean of 3.39 (Highly Satisfied).

This implies that Universal Bank clients find digital banking services highly efficient, as they offer convenience and save time by allowing transactions at any time of the day. From the client's perspective, the more convenient and user-friendly the digital banking platform, the greater their engagement and loyalty. Furthermore, the highest-rated aspect indicates that clients are highly adept at utilizing electronic banking efficiently, as it provides ease of use and smooth navigation across all service areas. However, the

lowest-rated indicators suggest that clients of Universal Bank are concerned about the risks associated with digital banking transactions. This highlights the need for Universal Bank to provide comprehensive webinars aimed at strengthening client awareness, equipping them with the knowledge to effectively protect themselves from potential cyber threats, and enhancing their overall satisfaction.

In line with this, Svitlana and Tetiana (2023) emphasized that digital transformation in financial institutions extended beyond technology, as it represented the fundamental foundation of banking and how it conducted business to provide excellent services to its clients. Furthermore, the digitalization of banking services benefited clients by allowing them to manage and access their accounts at any time of day, saving them time compared to conducting physical banking transactions. However, they additionally underscored the significant challenges of this digital adaptation, such as the population's low digital literacy, which caused financial constraints for clients seeking to maximize the adoption of electronic banking services.

Moreover, Bhutani (2023) emphasized that leveraging the advancement of electronic banking utilization provided clients with a secure platform to facilitate their financial transactions on a continuous basis, as well as 24/7 access to banking services. Furthermore, this significant improvement provided clients with convenience and positively reshaped their interactions with their bank as a result of streamlined services and an excellent banking experience.

Table 2.2

System Availability was Highly Satisfied (3.37). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Highly Satisfied. Indicator number 5 “Customers rarely encounter system errors or glitches when using electronic banking services.” had the highest mean of 3.40 (Highly Satisfied). Meanwhile, indicator 3 “Electronic banking services experience minimal downtime due to maintenance or system updates” had the lowest mean of 3.32, (Highly Satisfied).

This implies that Universal Bank clients find the digital banking platform highly reliable, providing them with extended convenience and a more straightforward navigation process that enhances their overall banking experience. The highest-rated indicator reflects strong client appreciation, as the platform's reliability ensures a seamless navigation process that encourages greater loyalty and productivity with Universal Bank.

Conversely, the lowest-rated indicator suggests that clients are dissatisfied with unscheduled system maintenance updates that cause unexpected transaction downtimes. This highlights the need for Universal Bank to improve its system error messaging by providing clients with prior and real-time updates on unavailable services during scheduled maintenance. By offering advance notice, clients can complete necessary transactions beforehand, enabling them to better tolerate and understand the importance of system updates for their security and protection.

According to M.Kathyaine (2024) electronic banking had significantly improved accessibility for clients who had been enrolled in electronic banking. This development allowed clients to conduct transactions at their own pace, saving time and enhancing their overall banking experience. For instance, they emphasized that more banks striven to innovate their digital services to provide an outstanding financial services experience. Banks had remained relevant and efficient by offering clients a seamless and innovative solution to their emerging banking needs.

Furthermore, Strohm (2023) demonstrated that electronic banking had provided users with greater accessibility by offering easy access features to effectively manage their finances and had given clients a variety of personalized banking solutions based on their own interests and financial needs. The wider system availability of digital banking had given Universal Bank extended opportunities to serve clients more efficiently and offered flexibility that connects people in conducting financial transactions in real-time and from any location.

Table 2.3

Fulfillment was Highly Satisfied (3.44). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Highly Satisfied. Indicator number 1 “Electronic banking services fulfill the needs of most customers” had the highest mean of 3.46 (Highly Satisfied). Meanwhile, indicator 2 “The availability of electronic banking services meets the demands of customers in terms of uptime and reliability.” had the lowest mean of 3.40 (Highly Satisfied).

This implies that the Universal Bank electronic banking services effectively addressed the needs of clients by offering a range of features designed to enhance convenience and provide them with a more personalized banking experience that significantly increased their transaction efficiency and reliability. Moreover, the highest indicator is applauded by Universal Bank clients for the significant effectiveness that greatly provides them with greater fulfillment. Meanwhile, the availability of electronic banking services meets the demands of customers in terms of uptime and reliability. This suggests that recalibrating the infrastructure of the electronic banking platform may provide a proactive system monitoring that is performed during peak-off maintenance for a more improved electronic banking uptime. This will help to reduce downtime and maintain service for greater availability and clients' digital banking experience.

Relative to the importance of fulfillment, Rupal & Singh (2023) recommended that the banking industry focus on the efficiency of its digital platforms to mitigate interruptions and technical issues that had caused frustration for clients. Furthermore, by addressing these issues, banks would provide a seamless and more efficient experience, leading to greater satisfaction. For instance, a bank's commitment was to provide excellent service quality to enhanced client loyalty, as clients had felt valued and confident while performing financial transactions through the bank's digital platform.

It is also worth mentioning that research conducted by Ayinaddis et al. (2023) stated that providing high-quality services was not only essential for retaining client loyalty

but, more importantly, for ensuring competitiveness and sustainability in the increasingly competitive digital banking industry. Moreover, providing quality electronic banking services fostered long-term client satisfaction, which was why the banking sector had needed to effectively revolutionize its digital transformation to enabled significant growth, drive innovation, and improved its global competitiveness. This digital transformation in the form of electronic banking services offered a more diverse range of banking products and services that were not limited by time or geography.

Table 2.4

Privacy was Satisfied (2.96). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Satisfied. Indicator number 1 “Electronic banking platforms adequately protect the privacy of customer data” had the highest mean of 3.11 (Satisfied). Meanwhile, indicator 4 “Electronic banking platforms promptly notify customers in case of any privacy-related incidents or breaches” had the lowest mean of 2.87 (Satisfied).

This implies that Universal Bank clients find electronic banking privacy to be satisfactory, providing them with the assurance that their private data is protected with the utmost diligence, which contributes to gained trust and client confidence. Furthermore, the highest indicator creates a satisfactory experience for clients, as they feel a sense of responsibility from Universal Bank to protect and secure client data to mitigate fraud.

On the other hand, the lowest indicator implies that most clients are not happy with the alertness of electronic banking in protecting their welfare from possible data breaches. This suggests that improvements should be made in the timeliness and sense of urgency of electronic banking notifications to enable quicker responses. It can be concluded that providing intensified protection for clients leads to greater trust and loyalty from the clients.

Furthermore, Rawwash et al. (2020) emphasized that in building client trust in the electronic banking system, privacy played a critical role in ensuring clients' confidence regarding the security of their data. Protecting client data during transactions should be a top priority, as electronic banking was expected to provide robust security to effectively safeguard sensitive information from the risk of fraud. Furthermore, clients' hesitation to fully embraced electronic banking was often due to the uncertainty they encountered while using these platforms. This uncertainty prompts banks to mitigate the potential risks of security features on digital platforms, recalibrate client perceptions, improved ease of use, and ultimately increased the adoption rate of electronic banking.

As evidenced by Gigante et al. (2022) who explored clients' preferences for traditional versus digital banking in a study involving 385 participants in Manila, Philippines. Interestingly, the findings revealed that clients preferred traditional banking, with 60.5% of response compared to full digital banking, which garnered 39.5%. These results indicated that despite the traditional banking taking more time for transactions, clients prioritized the assurance of security, efficiency, and personalized service. The findings suggested that the Philippine banking industry influenced client preference for

digital banking by improving factors such as efficiency, system availability, fulfillment, and privacy. This helped to increase client trust and confidence, ultimately leading to the successful adoption of electronic banking.

Research Question 3: Is there a significant relationship between the level of electronic banking utilization and the client satisfaction level in a Universal Bank in Laguna?

Table 3

There was a significant relationship between the level of electronic banking utilization and client satisfaction at Universal Bank in Laguna, as shown in Table 3. This was indicated by the positive correlations across all variables. Specifically, the correlations for website efficiency, user-friendliness, customer service, and security with the clients' satisfaction indicators, such as efficiency, system availability, fulfillment, and privacy, showed r values ranging from 0.353 to 0.777, which were interpreted as low positive to high positive correlations between electronic banking utilization and client satisfaction. The computed probability values of 0.000 were lower than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$), thus, null hypothesis was rejected.

This implies that the level of electronic banking utilization has a significant relationship with the client satisfaction level at Universal Bank in Laguna. Furthermore, improving the service quality of the electronic banking system will engage more usage and productivity with the utmost client trust and confidence. This means that the higher Universal Bank elevates the utilization of electronic banking, the higher client satisfaction will be generated.

The findings were supported by Tahtamouni (2022), who emphasized that electronic banking services had a positive and significant relationship with client satisfaction. This means that enhanced quality and availability of these services led to greater client satisfaction, as improved service features foster increased trust and engagement among users. It was concluded that Universal Bank should sustained the continuous innovation of digital technology to elevate electronic banking utilization and provide improved digital banking services for greater client satisfaction.

Similarly, Goveas & Kalluraya (2023) mentioned that financial institutions could have guaranteed client satisfaction by allocating funds to enhance the efficiency of their electronic banking systems, delivering fast, secure, and reliable digital services to clients. Moreover, consistently adding new features and improving service quality was crucial for building strong relationships with customers and adapting to their evolving preferences. Furthermore, they identified a positive and significant relationship between the utilization of electronic banking and the level of satisfaction experienced by clients.

Research Question 4: Does the level of electronic banking utilization significantly impact client satisfaction level in a Universal Bank in Laguna?

Table 4.1

There was a significant impact on the level of electronic banking utilization in terms of efficiency and client satisfaction at Universal Bank in Laguna. Based on the findings, electronic banking utilization significantly impacts client satisfaction. The probability values of .000, .001, and .013 were less than the level of significance at .05, thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This revealed that Website Efficiency, User-Friendliness, Customer Service, and Security play a substantial role, with the table explaining a 48.70 percent weighted score in Efficiency.

This suggests that all indicators of electronic banking utilization play a crucial role in delivering efficient digital services that enhance overall client satisfaction. Furthermore, these findings highlight the need for Universal Bank to continuously refine its electronic banking service quality by driving innovation and effectively assessing existing digital services. By doing so, the bank can better align with client expectations, ensuring an outstanding user experience and greater satisfaction.

In support of this findings, Rehman (2021) highlighted that the quality of electronic banking services was crucial to influenced client perceptions and experiences, thereby having a significant impact on their overall satisfaction. For instance, he explained that the digital transformation toward operational efficiency had a significant impact on client satisfaction by effectively maintaining competitiveness through constant digital innovation. For this reason, Universal Bank should prioritized enhancing the service quality of its electronic banking systems to improve user experience and increase the efficiency of digital banking services, ultimately leading to greater satisfaction.

Moreover, Daniela et al (2023) emphasized that while improving the service quality of electronic banking, banks should allocate funds to support the integration of system innovations to provide more efficient and reliable digital services to clients. Moreover, the study recommended that banks consistently develop new features to enhanced the client experience and confidence to create strong relationships and encouraging clients to fully maximize the use of digital platforms that led to a substantial impact on overall client satisfaction.

Table 4.2

There was a significant impact on the level of electronic banking utilization in terms of system availability and client satisfaction at Universal Bank in Laguna. This indicated that electronic banking utilization has a significant effect on client satisfaction in terms of system availability, which constitutes 49.2%. The probability values of .000, .001, and .025 were below the significance level of .05, thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. The results of the study revealed that Website Efficiency, User-Friendliness, Customer Service, and Security play a substantial role, with the table explaining a 49.2 percent weighted score in System Availability.

This implies that all indicators of electronic banking utilization are significant in providing efficient digital banking services to the client. In this reason, the Universal Bank should create substantial improvements in the electronic banking utilization for more convenience and reliability in the digital banking platform to generate a positive client experience.

Furthermore, Nilaish et al. (2024) mentioned that by utilizing the efficiency of modern technology, prioritizing system innovation, and maximizing technological advances, banks would create a more enhanced digital platform that provides clients with more flexibility, accessibility, and reliability using electronic banking platform that provides a significant impact towards clients' experience and happiness.

Table 4.3

There was a significant impact on the level of electronic banking utilization and client satisfaction at Universal Bank in Laguna, explicitly focusing on Fulfillment. This indicated that electronic banking utilization has a significant effect on client satisfaction in terms of fulfillment, which constitutes with probability values of .000 below the significance level of .05, thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. Meanwhile, with the probability values of .093 higher than the level of significance of .05, this implied that Customer Service of electronic banking in terms of fulfillment did not significantly impacted the client satisfaction, thus, the null hypothesis was accepted.

This implies that enhancing those components helps to improve the utilization of electronic banking, enhances the client experience by allowing them to navigate the platform to perform transactions without any delays, and provides the assurance of safety and security. This ultimately increased the client experience and effectively built trust, which positioned the bank competitively in the market.

In line with this, Le (2022) emphasized that increasing the service quality of electronic banking had an impact on client satisfaction, particularly when clients perceived higher efficiency, reliability, and security while conducting their business through digital banking. This action elevated the client banking experience at Universal Bank and created a significant impact on user fulfillment.

In view of Sasono et al. (2021), when clients faced technological challenges and difficulties during their processing times and required assistance in connecting to customer service, their level of satisfaction was likely to diminish significantly. To enhance the favorable client experience, banks should have intensified their efforts to promote the utilization of their electronic banking platforms, offering users a convenient, immediate, and reliable experience.

Table 4.4

There was a significant impact on the level of electronic banking utilization and client satisfaction at Universal Bank in Laguna, explicitly focusing on Privacy. This indicated that electronic banking utilization had a significant effect on client satisfaction in

terms of Privacy, which constitutes with a probability value of .000 significance level, thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. However, the probability values of .226, .408, and .546 were higher than the level of significance of .05, this implied that Customer Service, Website Efficiency, and User-Friendliness of electronic banking in terms of Privacy did not significantly impact client satisfaction, thus, the null hypothesis was accepted.

This implies that clients expect banks to safeguard their personal information and protect their welfare during transactions to prevent financial loss. This insight may help banks develop a secure platform that clients can use confidently while maximizing efficiency. However, despite banks' best efforts to protect client privacy, they continue to face vulnerabilities due to cyber threats.

Furthermore, Raza et al. (2024) discovered that the higher the level of security and privacy measures financial institutions incorporate into their digital banking services, the higher the client satisfaction. They found that security plays a crucial role in building trust, encouraging clients to use digital platforms. According to the authors, when clients felt secure about their personal information, they were more likely to engage with and remain loyal to their financial provider. This finding demonstrated that increasing the level of security on digital platforms positively impacts client experience and satisfaction.

Moreover, Debnath and Chellasamy (2022) mentioned that clients' perceptions of electronic banking services had a significant direct impact on their trust and confidence, encouraging them to maximize the use of digital banking services. These findings could help Universal Bank re-evaluate its existing privacy framework to ensure secure solutions that reduced online unauthorized activities and digital banking fraud.

Research Problem 5: Proposed Action Plan

As a result, a targeted action plan was proposed for the Universal Bank located in Laguna, aimed at optimizing the utilization of electronic banking and enhancing client satisfaction. This plan served as a roadmap to identify key areas such as electronic banking utilization (data security), client satisfaction (data privacy), and customer service. The action plan sought to improve the level of electronic banking data security to enhance user verification methods to prevent unauthorized access to create a safer digital financial environment while increasing clients' awareness by empowering users to take control of their data privacy through education and awareness programs on how effectively protect their private financial information. It also aims to collect user feedback to effectively drive the improvement of electronic banking, based on clients' evaluations, and to boost their confidence and overall experience while utilizing digital banking services.

Conclusions

1. That the level of electronic banking utilization at Universal Bank, among clients located in Laguna, is significantly influenced by factors such as website efficiency, user-friendliness, customer service, and security, which collectively impact the utilization of

electronic banking services. However, despite clients utilizing the electronic banking platform in terms of security, there is still hesitation in fully maximizing its effectiveness.

2. That the level of client satisfaction with electronic banking utilization in terms of efficiency, system availability, and fulfillment creates significant satisfaction in utilizing the digital banking platform. As evidence in the study, electronic banking utilization in terms of efficiency, system availability, and fulfillment are highly rated by Universal Bank clients, providing ease of use, accessibility, and reliability while utilizing electronic banking services. On the other hand, electronic banking utilization in terms of privacy is rated as satisfactory, as the majority of clients are not confident in the assurance that digital banking platforms would keep their data safe and protected.

3. That the level of electronic banking utilization and client satisfaction has a significant relationship, demonstrating that providing optimum service quality of digital banking services will elevate client trust and experience, which will lead to banks' greater competency. It concludes that banks should prioritize continuous improvement in the quality of their digital banking services, focusing on aspects such as website efficiency, user-friendliness, and customer service and security to not only enhance client satisfaction and trust but also position themselves for sustained growth and success in the competitive digital banking landscape.

4. That the significant impact exists between the level of electronic banking utilization and client satisfaction, indicating that continuously elevating the progress of innovation to increase electronic banking efficiency, system availability, fulfillment, and privacy creates enhanced service quality for a safer and more convenient digital banking experience for clients.

5. That an action plan was proposed to improve the level of electronic banking security in order to create a safer digital financial environment while increasing clients' awareness of how to effectively protect their private financial information through seminars. It also aims to collect customer satisfaction surveys to effectively drive the improvement of electronic banking.

6. That improving the service quality of the electronic banking system would increase usage and productivity, while elevating greater client trust and confidence. This means that the higher Universal Bank elevates the utilization of electronic banking, the greater the client satisfaction will be.

Recommendations

1. Universal Bank needs to prioritize the continuous innovation of electronic banking for better quality of its services. This suggests that the bank may improve its digital banking services by enhancing the existing security features and upgrading the one-time password system to multi-modal authentication, incorporating clients' fingerprints and facial recognition alongside the existing one-time password for triple-layer protection. This effectively provides extensive protection from cyber threats and digital

fraud. This feature will elevate the Universal Bank's digital banking security for greater safety and create a more positive digital banking experience for clients.

2. This suggests that attaining client satisfaction is essential in building competency in this era of global banking innovation, which is occurring across all financial institutions. The Universal Bank may enhance its client knowledge by offering quarterly webinars in electronic banking security and privacy awareness for clients who are interested in this matter. This educational awareness session will empower clients to increase their awareness of safer banking practices, which may help them recognize phishing scams, and encourage them to proactively protect their personal financial information, which will elevate trust and foster a stronger, more meaningful relationship between clients and Universal Bank.

3. The recommendation of providing consistent improvements to increase the optimum level of security and data privacy factors will provide clients a greater experience of electronic banking service quality, which will provide changes on how they will perceive and intend to use the electronic banking services with full confidence.

4. The Universal Bank may regularly collect clients' responses through surveys or feedback forms after transactions or at set intervals. This feedback will be analyzed on a monthly basis to identify pain points and areas for improvement. In platform updates are made quarterly or as needed, based on customer needs and preferences. This process will ease of use, reduce complaints, and ensure that positive feedback will be incorporated into future platform enhancements. Ultimately, it will boost retention and foster a more responsive service by recalibrating the main concerns of Universal Bank clients regarding their security and privacy while using digital banking services.

5. Enhancing data security, data privacy, and customer service, particularly in electronic banking utilization, is essential in elevating client satisfaction. Thus, Universal Bank in Laguna may prioritize this key area for more significant improvement in the quality of its electronic banking services. To achieve this, the bank may initially enhance the data security features of the digital banking platform to enhance user verification methods to prevent unauthorized access to increase the barrier against financial fraud. This was followed by increasing data privacy measures through quarterly seminars on electronic banking privacy protection to empower users to take control of their privacy through education and awareness programs. Lastly, a customer satisfaction survey is initiated to identify clients' preferences, particularly regarding data security and data privacy, in order to effectively evaluate and incorporate the results into the next scheduled update to improve customer experience.

6. The proposed action plan may suggest elevating the highest point of electronic banking service quality for more engagement and interactions coming from their clients, which will lead to more personalized connections and absolute trust for more harmonious business relationships.

7. Future researchers may conduct further studies on the factors contributing to security and privacy concerns in order to delve deeper into the factors influencing clients' perceptions of security and privacy risks, and their impact on the adoption of digital banking. Gaining a better understanding of these topics will help financial institutions to optimize their digital banking services, increase protection barriers, and further elevate client satisfaction.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study on electronic banking utilization and clients' satisfaction at Universal Bank in Laguna, Philippines, ethical considerations were a key focus in line with the research manual of LCBA, to ensure the well-being and privacy of participants, they were fully informed about the objectives of the study, their voluntary participation, and the confidentiality of their responses. Strong safeguards were implemented to ensure the protection of identity and data privacy during the entire process of data collection, processing, and dissemination. Moreover, the study adhered to ethical guidelines established by regulatory bodies, including the Data Privacy Act (DPA) of 2012, prioritizing transparency, respect, and goodwill. This approach aimed to maintain trust and integrity in the research project while preventing potential harm or discomfort to participants.

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